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ANALYSIS OF THE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

Objectives: The main objective of this study is analyzing and measuring the capability of improving and developing social enterprises in Uzbekistan. The theoretical basis of the scale is supported by empirical research in the social sector. On other hand, finding out both strengths and weaknesses on managing and developing environmental social entrepreneurship in our country also was our main aim in this article.

Methods. In this article we used SWOT analysis in order to identify the current condition of environmental social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. Besides that, variety kinds of tables and diagrams also created by author based on the information given by statistic committee.

Results. The results of this study analyses that social enterprises are required to report on the social and/or environmental benefits they bring to society, but in most countries, a uniform reporting form and criteria have not yet been developed in the area of control. In foreign practice, there are different definitions of social entrepreneurship, which sometimes contradict each other. According to experts, the complexity of developing a single legal approach to defining the term social entrepreneurship is explained by the following circumstances.

Conclusion. To conclude, environmental social entrepreneurship can be seen as an integral part of every single society and government future plans because of it vitalness and importance in today’s world. Because, tons of environmental and social problems are improving day by day instead of reducing. In order to solve aforementioned problems, social entrepreneurship is a most accurate choice in developing countries like Uzbekistan.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship; social and financial value; social and economic efficiency, social project, social benefit, project evaluation, project selection;

Introduction. In today's rapidly progressing and competitive world, more and more entrepreneurs are working at the intersection of philanthropy and commerce, innovation and traditional business practices to solve social problems in the world. Nevertheless, the legal aspects of the development of the phenomenon of "social entrepreneurship" are still in their initial stages.

The non-existence of the legal space of social entrepreneurship leads to negative consequences, such as the lack of development of rules for granting privileges and preferences, difficulties in buying and renting buildings, problems related to the sale of products, etc. Such difficulties are felt especially in the CIS countries, which pay special attention to social entrepreneurship.

In this regard, the study of the main trends in the field of legal regulation of social entrepreneurship in advanced countries such as the United States, Great Britain, Italy, Malaysia, and South Korea allows the following main points to be distinguished.

Methods. In order to develop social entrepreneurship plenty of works are doing step by step in Uzbekistan. Development of entrepreneurship, creation of new jobs, provision of employment of the population and increase of its income are considered to be one of the priority tasks in the current complex conditions. In this regard, our state and government are taking necessary measures to stabilize the economy and support business representatives.

Therefore, the coronavirus pandemic has shown that it is a very important and urgent task to develop production, increase the number of business entities, and especially to prevent a sharp decrease in the income of the low-income and unemployed segments of the population in order to increase the income of the population.

Today, it is an important task to introduce and develop non-state social protection policy, i.e., social entrepreneurship, taking into account international experiences and new approaches to solving socially important issues. Therefore, the draft law "On Social Entrepreneurship" defining the legal basis of the industry was developed.

The faction of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan in the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, among a number of issues on the agenda, this draft law was discussed in the second reading with the participation of deputies and representatives of official organizations. This draft law, discussed by the members of the faction, includes concepts such as the main principles of social entrepreneurship, the main directions of its activities, types of activities, and the main directions of the state policy in the field of social entrepreneurship¹⁸.

According to the draft law, new forms of state support for social entrepreneurship are being adopted to identify enterprises that have directed their resources to the social sphere, to take into account the privileges and

¹⁸ O.Otaxanova Can social entrepreneurship solve social problems in society? – 2020

preferences given for attracting investment into the social sphere.

In the project, based on their social importance, the persons belonging to the socially needy categories of the population are listed¹⁹:

- Persons with group I and II disabilities, children with disabilities;
- orphans and children deprived of parental care and persons aged 18 to 30 who belong to their category;
- persons suffering from socially significant diseases and diseases that pose a danger to others (tuberculosis, oncology, AIDS, leprosy and occupational diseases);
- single persons with dependent children under the age of 16 or with disabilities;
- graduates of general secondary, secondary special and professional educational organizations within 3 years of graduation;
- Graduates of orphanages under the age of 30;
- persons released from prisons;
- single elderly people who need the care of others and elderly people living alone;
- incompetent and disabled persons.

Forms of state support for social entrepreneurship social entrepreneurship activity by the state support is provided in the following forms²⁰:

- a) providing benefits and preferences;
- b) subsidizing social project costs;
- c) placement of the state social order;
- d) financial support;

e) training and retraining of social enterprise employees

f) providing advice, methodical assistance and informational support.

State support of social entrepreneurship activities is implemented from the day the business entity is entered into the register of social enterprises and is canceled from the day it is removed from the register of social enterprises.

State support for social entrepreneurship activities is applied to business entities that have changed their main activity in order to eliminate emergency situations only during the emergency period and is canceled from the first day of the month following the month in which the emergency situation was eliminated (cancelled).

Results. In accordance with the current legislation, tax and other benefits are established for enterprises that produce products and equipment for people with disabilities. However, the legal concept of social entrepreneurship and the mechanisms of legal regulation of relations related to it are not clearly provided for.

In this regard, when studying the legislation of the USA, Great Britain, Poland, Belgium, Italy and other countries, it can be seen that as a result of the establishment of this entrepreneurial activity, a high result has been achieved in terms of the production of social goods and the provision of social services, along with providing employment to the socially vulnerable sections of the population.

From this point of view, it was necessary to adopt the law "On Social

¹⁹ pf-26 on amendments and additions to certain documents of the president of the republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the improvement of the

system of social support for the elderly and people with disabilities–2021

²⁰ draft law on social entrepreneurship 17th substance

Entrepreneurship" in our country. Its main goal is to improve the living standards of the socially vulnerable population, provide them with work,

produce social goods and provide services.

To analyse current condition of SE in Uzbekistan more properly we utilized SWOT analysis.

Figure 1. SWOT analysis of the developing social entrepreneurship²¹

It can be transparently seen that there are huge opportunities to develop SE in Uzbekistan which brings plenty of positive effects to economy and environment. But, it is fair to say that SE does not come with negative affects like termination of activities of enterprises that harm the environment and unemployment of employees or violation of the healthy environment in the market by giving benefits to social entrepreneurship. From our point of view, SE has more advantages than its disadvantages. With the help of SWOT analysis we were able to find out external and internal factors which affects and effects social enterprises. (Figure 2)

In the development of social entrepreneurship aimed at environmental protection, it is important to study the

specific features of the environment affecting the industry and the interdependence of their constituent factors. Although external and internal factors affecting the development of social entrepreneurship based on environmental protection have not been systematized in the Republic of Uzbekistan, much attention is being paid to the greening of the economy. External factors affecting development do not depend on the social enterprise itself, these factors require support from the government and cooperation with other sectors.

Among the external factors, environmental factors and problems related to environmental damage in the country, as well as the socio-cultural level of the population occupy an important

²¹ Created by author

place. The creation of a favorable investment environment ensures the attraction of foreign investors in solving existing environmental problems and the study of foreign experience through them. The most important external factor in the development of social entrepreneurship is the government's support of the industry, which creates benefits for entrepreneurs and focuses on increasing their skills.

Internal factors also have a direct impact on the development of social entrepreneurship aimed at environmental protection. These factors mainly depend on

the skills of the social entrepreneur, such as his experience, level of understanding of the field, mastery of social entrepreneurship activities, thoroughness of the business plan, and the potential to use resources and modern technologies. In addition, the social and material benefit of entrepreneurs and how much of the income they can reinvest and how much they can use as they wish is the reason for the development of social entrepreneurship aimed at environmental protection by encouraging entrepreneurs.

Figure 2. External and internal factors affecting the development of social entrepreneurship based on environmental protection²²

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that in the context of the decrease in the rate of economic growth in the world and the socio-economic consequences of this trend have grown to an unforeseeable level, the governments of developed and developing countries are working to create legal foundations for social

entrepreneurship. they give priority to the development of effective measures.

From this point of view, in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of normative frameworks for the creation and development of the institution of social entrepreneurship, which provide for the system of full support by the state, including the announcement of

²² Created by author

subsidies and grants for them, benefits and it will be appropriate to provide preferences, as well as provide constant advisory support.

It is also important to take measures to inform the public and business circles about the benefits of social entrepreneurship.

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LEGAL REGULATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract:

Objective. The Economic Association of Interaction - individuals or legal entities, in order to combine the wines to maintain their independence, and the combined facilities. Corporation - for, to work in partnership to achieve common goals, united, independent legal entity - a legal person, the person described in the amount of medication. They are created in the form of joint stock companies. The concentration of enterprises is carried out in the form of cartel, syndicate, holding and financial-industrial groups.

Methods. In the process of analysis, methods of comparison and systematic analysis were used. The state of ensuring the development of sustainable development was assessed by the monitoring method and the corresponding conclusions were formed through abstract-logical thinking.

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